

Valorisation of residual biomass from the cultivation of olive trees in mountainous areas

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Abstract

Olive oil extraction is accompanied by the unwanted production of olive solid wastes and olive mill wastewater, with a high pollution potential. In addition to the above, olive leaves, olive tree branches from pruning and bark are usually burnt in site causing serious atmospheric pollution and increased risk for fires. However, valuable products can be extracted from this waste bio-mass.

In this work, expansion of existing small scale olive mills, usually encountered in mountainous areas of the Mediterranean region, are proposed. Their purpose will be to

extract high added value products from olive mill waste and olive cultivation waste biomass. Such products will be used for the treatment of human, animal or plant diseases either as stand-alone, or with other local herbs and medicinal plants.

Keywords: olive leaves, olive branches, herbs, olive-mills

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